

Simultaneous separation and preconcentration of rare earth elements on activated carbon for its determination by ICP-OES in beneficiation products

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Abstract : A simple, rapid, cost effective simultaneous separation and pre concentration method is developed for determination of rare earth elements in beneficiation products by inductively coupled plasma-optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES). The method is based on sorption of REEs on powered activated carbon (AC) in 3.4 M HF medium. The beneficiation products are decomposed by Na₂O₂ fusion followed by dissolution in HCl. Keeping in view its application to beneficiation products, experimental parameters such as effect of HF, amount of AC, contact time, sample weight were optimized for quantitative sorption. The REEs are desorbed quantitatively from activated carbon, by completely oxidizing and solubilizing AC by wet digestion (HNO₃ and HClO₄ treatment). Thus the time consuming and tedious method of ignition of charcoal to ashes is avoided, to increase the sample throughput in geochemical exploration studies. The precision of the method is $\pm 7\%$ at 1 ppm level. The accuracy of the method is evaluated by analyzing samples with oxalate precipitate separation procedure after fusion with Na₂O₂. The method is being applied on beneficiation products of various localities as a part of exploration of uranium. The method could be adopted by any laboratory as the input involved is inexpensive activated carbon associated with minimal skill unlike the reported methods of ion exchange and solvent extraction.

Keywords : Rare earth elements, beneficiation products, preconcentration, activated carbon, ICP-OES, wet ashing.

Introduction

Rare earth elements (REEs) are of great importance in terms of their geochemical properties, especially in geochemical exploration programmes and hence their precise determination is very important. The determination of REEs in geological samples is of great importance in exploration work, as it provides information on magma differentiation, metamorphic or other geochemical processes that may have taken place. In view of chemical similarities, REEs as a group serves, as indicator elements in petrography and ore deposit studies¹. The strategic and geochemical importance of REEs in view of their usage in electronics, super magnets, super conductors, high tech alloys² and marine geochemistry demands their determination in variety of samples from trace to percentage levels. Since the concentration of REEs in geological materials and in particular soil samples are at ppm and sub ppm levels, their direct determination is beyond the scope of ICP-OES. This necessitated for the development of preconcentration methods for the separa-

tion of REEs as a group from different matrices. The different preconcentration methods may be either physical methods or chemical methods. The most commonly used physical method based on specific gravity is wet tabling followed by bromoform separation and methylene iodide separation which is generally used to separate ferromagnesian minerals from quartz and feldspa³. The chemistry laboratory gets many of these beneficiated products including bromo heavies fractions for analysis of REEs for their distribution in these heavy minerals. Bromo heavies are rich in heavy minerals, iron and other elements which emits line rich spectrum and interfere in the analysis of heavy rare earth elements⁴⁻⁵. Hence, the separation of rare earth elements from iron rich matrix is necessary. The procedures generally followed for group separation of REEs are solvent extraction⁶, ion exchange⁷, co-precipitation⁸⁻¹⁰ and sorption. Among sorbents, the activated carbon is being widely used as a multi element trace collector¹¹⁻¹³ and used for separation and preconcentration of transition elements¹⁴, REEs¹⁵⁻¹⁷, pre-

cious metals¹⁸ from geological samples, for determination by various instrumental techniques. In the present investigations, the authors based on their previous published work¹³⁻¹⁷ extended application of activated carbon further to separate REEs from bromo heavies and the results are discussed in this paper.

Experimental

Instrumentation :

All ICP-OES measurements were made using Ultima 2 model (Horiba Jobin Yvon, France), equipped with a computer controlled rapid scanning monochromator. The operating conditions for ICP-OES are given in Table 1. The wavelengths used for measurement of rare earth elements, background corrections applied, background equivalent concentrations and detection limits are given in Table 2.

Reagents/Apparatus :

Powdered activated carbon (AC, Merck) was used for

the sorption studies, after purifying it with repeated treatment of hydrochloric acid of appropriate concentration.

Hydrofluoric acid (proanalysis, 40% GR, Merck) used as an acid medium for sorption of REEs on activated carbon.

Hydrochloric acid (ExcellR, Qualigens) and sodium peroxide (GR, Merck Ltd.) were used for sample decomposition and dissolution of REES after separation by solid phase micro extraction.

Nitric acid (ExcellR, Qualigens) and perchloric acid (GR, Merck Ltd.) were used for desorption of REEs by solubilising carbon through oxidation.

REEs standard stock solution of 1000 µg/ml was prepared from high purity oxides (99.99 or 99.999%, Johnson Matthey) as per the standard procedures. The working standards of 5 µg/ml and 0.5 µg/ml were used for La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm; further 2.5 µg/ml and 0.25 µg/ml were used for Gd, Tb, Er; and finally 0.5 µg/ml and 0.05 µg/ml were used for Eu, Dy, Ho, Tm, Yb, Lu, Y. These solutions were made by appropriate dilution of stock solutions.

Plastic beakers, glass beakers and plastic rods cleaned repeatedly with hydrochloric acid and quartz distilled water before use for sorption studies in HF medium.

Procedure :

(a) Preparation of sample solution :

A 0.5 g amount of finely powdered bromo heavies sample (~200 mesh) was taken in a nickel crucible and 3-4 g of sodium peroxide was added to it. The nickel crucible was kept on burner till clear red hot melt is obtained. The crucible is kept for cooling and the fused melt is leached with distilled water in a beaker and dissolved in hydrochloric acid. The clear solution, thus obtained, was transferred to plastic beaker (250 ml).

(b) Sorption of REEs on activated carbon :

From the above sample solution, the hydroxides of REEs, Fe, Ti etc. were precipitated (using ammonia solution), filtered (Whatman 541), washed and transferred back into the same plastic beakers quantitatively, with a fine jet of distilled water. The precipitate was dissolved, using 15 ml of HF and the volume was made to ~100 ml. Then 0.5 g of purified AC was added and two hours of contact time was maintained, with frequent stirring.

Table 1. ICP-OES instrumental parameters and operating conditions

Rf Generator	40.68 MHz
Forward power	1000 W
Reflected power	< 5 W
PMT voltage	600 V
Integration time	0.5 s
Entrance slit	21
Exit slit	15
Argon gas flow rates	PL1 = 12 L/min G1 = 0.2 L/min
Viewing mode, height	Radial, 11 mm
Nebulizer pressure	2.64
Sample uptake rate	0.7 ml/min
Monochromator	Modified Czerny-Turner
Grating	4320 grooves mm ⁻¹ and 2400 grooves mm ⁻¹ (back to back)
Ruled area	110 mm × 80 mm
Focal length	1000 mm
Wavelength range	165-800 nm
Wavelength resettability	± 0.001 nm
Dispersion	0.005 nm mm ⁻¹ (first order)
Slits	21 µm entrance, and 15 µm exit
Detector	Photomultipliers R-106
No. of steps and time	15 steps, 0.5 s
Observation height	11 mm above load coil

Table 2. Spectral lines used for emission measurement of lanthanides, BG correction points, BEC, L/B and D.L. values

Element	Wavelength (nm)	Background correction		Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	BEC ^a ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	L/B	D. L. ^b ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)
		Left (nm)	Right (nm)				
La	333.749	-	0.0167	1	0.0571	18	0.0017
Ce	418.660	0.0095	-	1	0.2005	5	0.0060
Pr	422.293	0.0216	0.0122	1	0.6433	2	0.0193
Nd	430.357	0.0155	-	1	0.2486	4	0.0075
Sm	359.262	0.0159	-	1	0.2656	4	0.0080
Eu	381.965	0.0189	-	1	0.0198	50	0.0006
Gd	342.246	0.0136	-	1	0.1037	10	0.0031
Tb	350.917	0.0178	-	1	0.1293	8	0.0039
Dy	353.170	0.012	-	1	0.0241	41	0.0007
Ho	345.600	-	0.0214	1	0.0771	13	0.0023
Er	349.910	-	0.0118	1	0.0486	21	0.0015
Tm	346.221	0.00978	-	1	0.0288	35	0.0009
Yb	328.937	-	0.0111	1	0.0082	121	0.0002
Lu	261.542	-	0.0126	1	0.0099	101	0.0003
Y	371.029	-	0.012	1	0.0097	103	0.0003

(-) Background correction points not applied.

^aBEC is calculated from : Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) $I_b/(I_p - I_b)$, where I_p and I_b represents peak counts and background counts respectively.

^bD.L. is calculated based on three times the standard deviation of the blank at 1% RSD (D.L. = BEC \times 0.03).

The solution containing AC was filtered through plastic funnel (Whatman 540) to separate out AC containing sorbed REEs quantitatively and washed, first with HF (0.2 M) twice and then with distilled water twice.

(c) Desorption of REEs :

The carbon substrate containing REEs was quantitatively transferred into beaker-A (glass) with a fine jet of water and dilute nitric acid (30% v/v). The filter paper containing traces of AC adhered to it was immersed in (separate beaker- B) in about 30 ml of nitric acid (30% v/v), boiled and the supernatant solution was transferred back into the beaker-A. The whole solution was boiled nicely to oxidize the easily oxidisable organic matter and when the volume was around 50 ml, perchloric acid was added (5 ml) and the boiling was continued till the carbon is completely oxidized and solubilized leaving behind clear solution containing REEs. The volume was made up to 25 ml and aspirated into ICP-OES for determination of individual REEs at the wavelengths mentioned in Table 2.

Results and discussion

In the process of physical beneficiation by wet tabling

followed by bromoform separation, the heavier mineral fractions are separated from the rest of ore body to study the association of uranium with other matrix. Hence, the samples are sent to chemistry laboratory for chemical characterization of beneficiation products including bromo heavies for analysis of individual REEs, uranium and heavy elements. Since the bromo heavies/beneficiation products are low in silica and rich in heavy minerals, the usual open acid digestion method with HF-HNO₃ treatment could not bring the sample completely into solution, and fusion methods were used for complete decomposition of these beneficiation products. Among the various fusion fluxes [Na₂CO₃, Na₂O₂, (KHF₂ + NaF), KHSO₄], fusion with Na₂O₂ fusion and dissolution in 5% HCl gave a complete clear and stable solution, since these beneficiation products are rich in iron, titanium and other heavy metals which interfere in the analysis of individual REEs by ICP-OES. Also, the fused solutions contain lot of salt content along with crucible material and hence direct determination by ICP-OES is not possible, as the concentric nebulizer tolerates only 0.5% of total dissolved solids. In order to achieve better determination limits, it becomes necessary to separate REEs from bulk matrix.

The solvent extraction³ separation involves the use of expensive extractants like tri-*n*-octyl phosphine oxide, tri-*n*-butyl phosphate, di ethyl hexyl phosphoric acid etc. It also requires skilled personnel for separation process apart from being time consuming. The cation and anion exchange separation methods⁴ results in high elution volume and are time consuming. The co-precipitation methods^{6,7} based on hydroxide-fluoride or hydroxide-oxalate precipitation involves the addition of different carriers, thus making these separation methods more cumbersome and time consuming apart from requirement of a separate preconcentration step. The reported co-precipitation and co-precipitation/ion exchange separation¹⁹ methods for determination of REEs in various geological samples are complex, involves the addition of carrier and hence not suitable to handle large number of samples. The author also used phosphate flux for decomposition of bromo heavies and separated REEs from major matrix as oxalates²⁰ and applied on samples having very high concentration of REEs. In the present work, authors have developed a method for application to bromoheavies containing low concentration of REE.

For application to geochemical exploration samples, separation and preconcentration procedure has to be simple, rapid, involving minimal skills and also results in higher sample throughput. In the previous published work, the activated carbon was extensively used for separation of transition elements¹¹, precious metals¹⁸ and REEs^{12,13,16,17} from a variety of geological samples for application to geochemical exploration work to increase the sample throughput and to make the preconcentration method so simple that any laboratory could adopt.

In the present work, the activated carbon has been used for separation and preconcentration of REEs in bromo heavies/beneficiation products. Keeping in view chemical composition of bromo heavies samples given in Table 3, the optimal parameters such as HF concentration, amount of AC, contact time, sample weight, sample

solution volume are redefined by taking synthetic sample solution matrix matched with respect to bromo heavies under investigation. Following optimal conditions are recommended for quantitative separation of REEs from bromo heavies and subsequent sorption on activated carbon, based on experiments.

Sample weight : 0.5–1.0 g (variable)

Sample solution volume : 25 ml (variable)

HF concentration : 3.4 M

Quantity of AC : 0.5 g

Contact time : 1 h

The REEs from the AC were recovered by wet ashing of charcoal using combination of acids HNO₃ and HClO₄. Initially boiling of AC with concentrated HNO₃ helps in oxidizing the easily oxidizable organic matter, followed by boiling the solution with 5 ml of perchloric acid which helps in completely oxidizing and solubilising activated carbon, leaving a clear solution containing REEs. In fact the complete oxidation of carbon is only observed, when the volume is about 5 ml. This method of wet digestion results in high sample throughput as the dependence on platinum dishes for dry ashing to recover REEs is avoided. A batch of 24 sample solutions could easily be taken up in plastic beakers for separation and preconcentration of REEs on AC. As reported¹⁶ the probable mechanism for sorption of REEs on AC in hydrofluoric acid medium could be due to sorption of hydrophobic fluoride species. Some selected bromo heavies samples were analyzed by present method and the results are given in Table 4.

The procedural blank of the method is low due to rejection of alkali, alkaline earth and other associated major elements of sample matrix by activated carbon in HF medium when compared with phosphate fusion followed by separation of REEs as oxalates (easily ionisable alkali metals suppresses the emission signal and are with REEs fraction). This method can also be applied to samples having REEs at low level. Another major advantage of this method is, it avoids the use of expensive platinum ware.

Accuracy and precision :

Since the certified reference materials for bromo heavies/beneficiation products are not available in our labora-

Table 3. Major element composition of beneficiation products

Sl. no.	Sample no.	%Al ₂ O ₃	%Fe ₂ O ₃	%TiO ₂	%MnO	%CaO	%MgO
1.	BH-1	4.27	47.99	9.31	0.59	2.01	0.76
2.	BH-2	5.44	34.59	5.59	0.42	5.49	1.91
3.	BH-3	4.50	37.17	3.25	1.91	4.23	2.59
4.	BH-4	9.53	22.70	10.24	0.77	6.90	1.21

Table 4. REEs data in some bromo heavies analysed by present method

Element (ppm)	BH-1	BH-2	BH-3	BH-4
La	4706	258	718	47
Ce	11109	394	1352	117
Pr	1220	50	114	14
Nd	7334	184	534	70
Sm	3507	35	132	18
Eu	72	5	30	4
Gd	3757	28	85	31
Tb	845	5	10	7
Dy	5230	28	34	44
Ho	1014	7	5	10
Er	3308	17	15	31
Tm	608	<5	<5	<5
Yb	4788	13	10	27
Lu	825	<5	<5	5
Y	29220	258	130	280

tory, the accuracy of present method was checked by analyzing the same samples by an alternative separation method by separating REEs, as oxalates and the results obtained are given in Table 5. The values obtained by both the methods are in close agreement with each other. The precision of the method varies from 5–7% (n = 4).

Table 5. Evaluation of accuracy of REEs data in few bromo heavies samples

Element (ppm)	BH-1		BH-4	
	A	B	A	B
La	4706	4650	47	42
Ce	11109	11092	117	110
Pr	1220	1229	14	12
Nd	7334	7345	70	75
Sm	3507	3487	18	20
Eu	72	70	4	3
Gd	3757	3775	31	26
Tb	845	850	7	6
Dy	5230	5210	44	40
Ho	1014	1005	10	11
Er	3308	3319	31	35
Tm	608	600	<5	<5
Yb	4788	4765	27	24
Lu	825	810	5	4
Y	29220	29200	280	275

A – Present method.

B – Na₂O₂ fusion followed by oxalate precipitation method.

In the proposed AC based preconcentration method, the greatest advantage is that more than 99.5% of the major matrix is left behind and the REEs are preferentially adsorbed on AC. The final concentration of total dissolved salts is <0.5%, which is best suited for concentric nebulizer attached to ICP systems for better precision.

Conclusion

The proposed method is simple, economical (due to use of inexpensive reagent i.e. activated carbon) and involves minimal skills, unlike other reported separation methods. Since more than 99.5% salt matrix could be separated, the method is best suited for ICP instruments fitted with concentric nebuliser to take advantage of high precision and superior detection limits. The method is suitable for separation of REEs from bromo heavies/beneficiation products and the method could be easily adopted by any laboratory as the inputs are minimal (only AC), there is no need of costly platinum ware.

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